

MANAGEMENT OF ATISARA (DIARRHOEA) WITH DIET (PATHYAPTHYA) FROM AYURVEDA PERSPECTIVE: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Atisara (diarrhoea) is a fairly prevalent disease in the modern day, due to irregular and harmful practices related to *ahara* and *vihara*, which cause *sharia* and *manavaigunyata* (physical and psychological involvement). Although *atisara* (diarrhoea) rarely poses a threat to health, it can persist and be quite painful. *Atisara* (diarrhoea) is becoming more common every day. Because of the influence of western eating habits, bad nutrition practices and mental stress. Here, we address *Nidana Panchaka* with a focus on *Samprapti* of *Atisara* (diarrhoea) as mentioned in *Ayurvedic* literature. Understanding the *Nidana Panchaka* and the *samprapti* in-depth allows for the formulation of appropriate management of diet (*Ahara*) for preventive measures of *Atisara*.

INTRODUCTION

Diarrhea is vital public fitness problem amongst children in India. Diarrhea is a leading cause of deaths in children,

accounting for approximately 9 per cent of all deaths among children in worldwide in 2021. This translates to over 1,200 young children dying each day, i.e about 4,44,000 children a

year, despite the availability of a simple treatment solution. For diarrhea. Mandagni is the most significant factor in the pathogenesis of Atisara (diarrhoea). Mandagni is the underlying cause of amadosha and a key factor in the presentation of most disorders, including Atisara (diarrhea). Amadosha is the consequence of agnidushti brought on by mithya-aharavihara (mal practice of food and conduct), and it eventually takes the form of Atisara (diarrhea). Therefore poor eating habits are significant factor in the development of atisara (diarrhoea), and advice to practise correct ahara-vidhividhana is part of the treatment. The digestive system in humans is incredibly sensitive and reacts to both internal bodily processes and emotional states appropriately.

Nidanas of Atisara (Etiology)

As due to infection acquired through the oral route or by ingestion of contaminated food and water associated with poverty, poor hygiene enteropathogens like shigella, E.coli, rotaviruses, colera, vibrio & salmonella etc.

CLASSIFICATION OF DIARRHEA

According to duration

1. Acute diarrhea
2. Chronic diarrhea.

According to mechanism

1. Osmotic diarrhea
2. Secretory diarrhea
3. Exudative or inflammatory diarrhea

Patho – physiology

The major mechanism responsible for the diarrhea is injury to the mucosal surface of GIT, which impairs the normal absorptive & secretory balance of different regions of guts resulting in diarrhea. Viral pathogens produce injury to proximal small bowel & bacterial pathogens usually cause colonic injury.

According to ayurveda texts, nidanas (causes) of Atisara can be identified under four broad headings as viz. Aharaja, viharaja, manasika (emotional etc.) and agantuja (external factors viz. Bacteria, virus etc.) nidanas.

Acharya Sushruta in Uttarasthana mentions guru (heavy), snigdha (unctuous), ruksha (dry), ushna (hot), drava (liquid), sheeta padartha sevanana, sanyoga viruddha, samskara viruddha ahara sevana, adyasana (eating before the digestion of previous meal), ajeerna, asathmya bhojana, increased snehapana, bhaya (fear), visha (use of poison), shoka (grief), dushta ambu-paana (drinking of contaminated water), madyapana (alcohol consumption), rithusaathmya (change of season of physical contrarities), vega varodha (suppression of natural urges), krimi and arshas.

Acharya also mentioned that atisara can also be caused due to krimii.e, pathogens like bacteria, amoeba, viruses etc. as told in contemporary science.

Vagbhataa charya opines that consumption of rukshamamsa, mamsa derived from lean animals or preparations of tila or germinating seeds, Krimi and Arshas³ are responsible in causation of Atisara (diarrhea).

Samprapti (Pathophysiology)

Samprapti Ghatakas

1. Doshas-Vata-Pradhana Tridoshaja
2. Dushaya-Udaka, Purisha
3. Agni-Jatar Agnimandya
4. Ama-Ajeerna-Jnyaama/Mandagni-Jnyaama
5. Srotas-Purishvah, Udakavaha, Annava-ahasrotas
6. Srotodusti-Ati-pravarti
7. Udbhava-sthan-Pakwashaya
8. Adhithana-Pakawashaya/guda
9. Svabhava-Ashukari
10. Sadhyasadhyata-Kruchasadhyas/sadhya.

Lakshanas (Sign and Symptoms)

Type of Atisara and their Lakshanas

1. Vataja Atisara

1. The stool is slimy and mixed with Mucus (Ama)
2. The stool floats on water
3. The stool is rough and liquid
4. Defecation is associated with colic pain

5. Colic pain is brought on by the exacerbated Vayu (flatus), which moves obliquely in the Kostha (gastrointestinal tract) and makes gurgling noises.

2. PittajaAtisara

1. The patient voids frequent loose motions which are either yellow, green blue or black in color
2. The stool is mixed with blood and bile, and it is excessively foul smelling and
3. The patient suffers from Trishna (excess thirst), Daha (burning sensations, Atisweda(excessive sweating), Murcha (fainting), etc.

3. KaphajaAtisara

1. The patient voids stool which is Snigdha (unctuous), Shwetam (white), Picchila (slimy), mixed with mucus as well as undigested food particles, Guru (heavy), Durgandham (foul-smelling).
2. Badhhashoola (continuous pain)
3. Pravahikam
4. Heaviness in the abdomen, in the region of urinary bladder and in the pelvic region
5. The patient feels the urge for passing another bout of stool even after evacuation.
6. Loma harsha (horripilation), Utklesha (Nausea), Atinidra (excessive sleep), Aalasya (indolence), Sadana (prostration) and Annadvishi (dislike for food).

4. Sannipataja Atisara

1. Stool having yellow (like the color of turmeric), green, blue, reddish (like the meat is Manjistha), pink (like the color of water in which meat is washed), red black, white and yellowish (like the color of the pig-fat) in color.
2. The patient suffers from continuous pain.
3. All the symptoms mentioned in vataja, pittaja and kaphajaatisara.

Shokaja and bhayaja

This sort of diarrhoea is brought on by sadness or fear. These emotional variables vitiate pitta and vata, which results in atisara, or frequent passing of watery stools.

Treatment of Atisara (Diarrhoea) from Ayurvedic perspective

Nidana parivarjana: It is nothing but avoid the causes of atisara, such as drinking too much water, eating too much, not spacing meals out enough, drinking bad water, or eating particularly hot, dry, hard, cold, or unfamiliar foods.

Shamanachikitsa: It consists of pacification methods for the prakupita doshas by following methods.

- i. Langhana: This involves fasting or eating fewer or smaller portions of food, which aids in the body's digestion of ama and eliminates the disease's primary cause.
- ii. Pachana and deepana: Foods that increase appetite and digestives help the body get rid of ama more quickly by strengthening the digestion fire.

Diet for Atisara as Pathyapathya

Ayurveda deals extensively with pathyapathya, also known as upashaya anupashaya of Atisara. Fruits, grains, and hot water are categorised as pathya in the Kasyapa Samhita, while apathya includes the consumption of lashuna (garlic), sweet substances, meat soup, and sudation. A detailed explanation of pathyaapathya has been provided by Yogaratnakara. Important pathya include nidra, langana, milk from cows and goats, ghrita, butter made from cow or goat milk, and curd, buttermilk made from cow or goat milk. Apathya includes eating and drinking a lot of calories.

At appropriate meal time, if the patient feels hungry, light food should be given to eat. It enhances the appetite and stimulates agni and as a result the strength is promoted immediately.

Depending upon the whole someness (satmya) of the patient, light food along with buttermilk or kanji (a sour drink), yavagu (thick gruel), tarpana or alcoholic drink or honey should be given. Then gradually yavagu (thick gruel), vilepi (a sticky gruel), khanda (a sour appetiser), yusha (vegetable soup) and boiled rice mixed with meat soup which are prepared by adding digestive stimulants and astringent (constipative) drugs should be given.

Ingredients which are dipana (digestive stimulant) and grahi (constipating) are described in (Cha. Sa. Sutra Sthana 4/9) should be administered¹⁵ A proper diet plan should be followed for the prevention and the cure of atisara (Diarrhoea). A proposed diet chart has been explained below.

	Timing	Food item options (for vegetarians and for non-veg)	Serving size details	Other details
Wake up drink	5.30 am to 6 am	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BalaBilva Juice • Coconut water • Dhanyakahima (dhanyaka kept in water over night) • Chandan with madhu+sharkra drink 	01 cup–50/100 ml	Should cover properly night
	6 am to 7 am			• Cooling Pranayama
Morning drinks	6 am to 7 am	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lemon tea /Green tea 	01 cup–50/100 ml	Ginger should be added in tea preparation
Breakfast	9 am	Main dish <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mudgadasha with navneet • Uradadosha 		Chapati should be serve with cow/goat ghee
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chappathi (2/3) with goduma/ yava 		
		Curry / chutney <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sambar with less dal • Balabilva + ginger chutney • Aamlaki chutney 		
Drinks		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bilva juice • Black jeera water • Dhanyaka water • Carrot juice • Radish juice • Alovera juice with honey • Watermelon juice • Takra • Moong + Uradpeya (Bala, Shtavri siddha) • Vilepi (Jiraka and Ajmoda) • Moolak Yush • Shtavri Bala Ksheerpaka 	I cup – 100 ml on each serving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Panaka 1 part drug and • Panakas can change 16 part water. daily <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ginger/ lemon and ela can be added in juice
Lunch	1 to 2 pm	Main dish <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shali rice / brown rice 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It should consume hot in nature should have any above • In between food one mentioned Yusha which is hot in nature
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chappathi (2/3) with godhuma / yava With little amount of ghee 		
		Sabji <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drumstick subji • Banana flower subji • Pumpkin sabji • Radish subji • Cluster bean sabji • Bitterguardsabji • Mugdasabji • Subji prepared with bean 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lemon pickle • Amlaki pickle • Carrot pickle
		Curry		

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sambar with drumstick • Curd curry with ginger, jeera. • Kushmanda dhal curry • Dhanyayusha • Moong dal and old rice krishra with curd • Khadayusha Mamsa <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goat • Hen • Sheep 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small fishes Salads and fruits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water melon • Apple • Radish • Blurberry (Jambu) 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banana • Lemon <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Muskmelon 		
Evening snacks/ snacks all over day	5 pm - 6 pm	Green tea / Herbal tea/Lemon tea	01 cup – 100 ml	
Dinner	8 pm	Main dish <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peya with rice and mudga • Brown rice /rice • Chappati with yava Sabji <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kushmandasabji • Bottle guard sabji • Snake guard subji Curry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rasam with ginger • Mudgadaal • Masoordaal 		
Other advices	-	-	-	Practice Cooling Pranayama <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shitli • Shitkari
Apathya	Ahara <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Leafy Vegetables (Patrashaka) • Garlic • Sugarcane • Wheat (Godhum) • Black gram • Mango • Aamalki • Barley • Betel nuts • Drakshaw 			

- Ruksha, Guru, UshnaAahara
- Spicy salt food, (Lavana and Amla Rasa)
- Cow meat
- Vihara**
- Malavegadharana
- Ativyayama
- Aatapasevana
- Masnika**
- Kroda
- Shoka
- Bhaya

DISCUSSION

As mentioned in Ayurvedic text, Dosh Dushti is Pitta pradhan Tridosh dushti, as there is Amlodgar, Urodaha, Trushna lakshnas present. Due to increased Drava, Sara and Ushnaguna of Pitta leads to Agninash and Purishbheda.

Atisara leads to the depletion of water and beneficial salts causing dehydration in the body.

This provokes vata, and therefore requires taking special care of vata, particularly if, the atisara is caused by all the three dosha. Hydration of the body by means of oral administration of milk, buttermilk and various liquid preparations is advised. Goat's milk is very useful in Raktaja diarrhoea. Hence adequate prophylaxis measures should be taken to prevent the infectious diarrhoea.

The unripe fruit is said to be an excellent remedy for diarrhoea and is especially useful in chronic diarrhoeas. The effectiveness of *A. marmelos* fruit in diarrhoea and dysentery has resulted in its entry into the British Pharmacopoeia. More over, Chopra has appropriately stated that "No drug has been longer and better known nor more appreciated by the inhabitants of India than the Bael fruit." Charaka has described this plant as a Rasayana.

CONCLUSION

Sangrahi (astringent or anti-diarrheals) therapies are not advisable in the initial stage of the disease because of presence of ama inside the body. Instead, mild laxative should be given to eliminate the accumulated dosha. Diarrhea should be allowed to continue and should not be stopped by constipating or bowel binding drugs. The patients shall be managed with light to digest, nutritive and liquid diet regimen which enhances the power of agni as well as it helps to stop diarrhea.

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